

BOOST 4.6 - Recommendation for improving the interoperability of Data Analysis Platforms

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Introduction

NERC has managed data access and sharing policies since its creation in 1965. Today, the Environmental Data Service (EDS)¹ provides integrated data services across its five data centres, including operational analysis platforms, across all NERC² domains. Most science applications are becoming increasingly multidisciplinary; The EDS is working towards providing environmental data users with a “one stop shop” for data services. The EDS forms part of NERC’s digital strategy and implementation, working across discipline boundaries to break down barriers and facilitate data sharing.

The EDS, with partners, will pilot cloud native FAIR data services to support cross-disciplinary, pan-UKRI applications which increasingly need to combine diverse data and knowledge of the underpinning measurement and data capabilities. These services will extend our DRI Phase 1b developments of core NERC data services, building on international standards and data commons principles to link to existing cross-council DRI developments. The BOOST project has addressed :

- Data findability and traceability through Persistent Identifier registration and asset cataloguing with a novel linking of provenance via semantic graphing techniques.
- Extend data accessibility and interoperability by continuing to develop a federated Trusted Research Environment on JASMIN, ensuring compliance with DARE UK standards.
- By building on the EDS DataLabs data processing environment, create workflow services to process, quality assure and integrate large-scale genomics data that describe biodiversity.
- Enhance interoperability across disciplines by performing a detailed review of analysis platforms across disciplines and user applications, leading to recommendations for FAIR implementation.
- Support all of the above through a coordinated framework of co-creation of services and associated training with users.

¹ <https://eds.ukri.org/environmental-data-service>

² <https://www.ukri.org/councils/nerc/>

This document is concerned with activities on Work Package 4 which performed a review of Analysis Platforms with Recommendations for Interoperation. NERC and UKRI have many data analysis platforms designed to accommodate individual communities, workflows and available resources. We will exploit the RDA³ framework, emerging global trans-disciplinary standards and also develop links with CEOS⁴ and other trailblazing community groups to establish best practice. The recommendations will inform FAIR data services working within a CARE compliant framework⁵.

Work Package 4 Deliverables:

- BOOST D4.1: Working Group, Workshops, User Survey and Key Reports
- BOOST D4.2: Progress with establishing a TRE on JASMIN and utilising workflows - May 9th Workshop
- BOOST D4.3: CEOS Jupyter Notebooks Best Practice V1.1
- BOOST D4.4: NERC DataLabs Fair Interoperability
- BOOST D4.5: Inter-platform/archive workflows and use cases for RO-Crates
- BOOST 4.6: Recommendation for improving the interoperability of Data Analysis Platforms (**This Document**)

In this document BOOST D4.6 we provide a summary of recommendations that have emerged from Work Package 4. We carefully considered recommendations that would have impact and bring our data to a broader audience in addition to improving the service provided to our traditional communities. In our analysis we carefully considered the skills barriers and how our data needs to be discoverable by blending with the software, environments, working practices and cultures of new users in universities, government departments and industry.

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

⁴ <https://ceos.org/>

⁵ https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5d3799de845604000199cd24/t/6397b363b502ff481fce6baf/1670886246948/CARE%2BPrinciples_One%2BPagers%2BFINAL_Oct_17_2019.pdf

Pilot for Inter-platform/archive workflows captured by RO-Crates

In this document D4.5: Interplatform workflows and potential use cases for RO-Crates we consider the importance of workflows connecting up archives and data analysis platforms. As we discovered from the survey and working group discussions, in addition to simply moving data from archive to platform; there is the need to extract, transform, compress data and document uncertainties associated with any transformation. The ability to capture reusable workflows can produce efficiency savings. It could also increase data use by communities who do not have sufficient skills/resources to produce their own workflows but would greatly benefit from the output.

We recommend the trial of technologies such as RO-Crates⁶, Common workflow language⁷ and cloud optimized formats listed under D4.5. We identified some key areas that would benefit from inter-platform/archive workflows that could be used in a pilot project. We recommend some of these ideas be progressed to mature use cases and implemented in order to fully evaluate the technologies.

Another important aspect of developing these capabilities is the potential for international alignment. As we see infrastructures tending towards federation on an international level and adopting RO-Crate technologies, they may access resources on the European Open Science Cloud⁸ through project such as FAIR2Adapt⁹. These approaches will target common UK/European data investments such as ECMWF¹⁰ and the ESA Digital Twin¹¹ the ability to align and share workflows produced would be to the UK's benefit.

The use of executable workflows could also be a way of de-risking government investment. A lot of research is ongoing with respect to standardisation through OGC¹² and subsequent scaling of workflows into services. Where workflows can be created at lower cost, if they gain sufficient traction with communities, creation of new datasets or services can be justified at a much lower risk level. This approach could also generate commercialization opportunities and be used beyond the environment science domain, with captured executable workflows becoming a key of national infrastructure.

⁶ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

⁷ <https://www.commonwl.org/>

⁸ <https://eosc.eu/>

⁹ <https://eosc.eu/eu-project/fair2adapt/>

¹⁰ <https://www.ecmwf.int/>

¹¹ <https://dte.esa.int/>

¹² <https://www.ogc.org/>

Pilot for EDS Jupyter Notebooks Repository

Jupyter Notebooks have an important role in the use of EDS data. As described above, Jupyter Notebooks have an important part to play in the capture of key analysis processes and workflows. They have also become a staple of training provision. Many projects automatically produce key tools for new data users as they are highly effective in lowering skills barriers. While they certainly are not the only tool in use by EDS, they are the most prevalent.

There has long been a tension in archives as to whether they should attempt to preserve dataset specific software and tools along with data. This is due to their relatively short shelf life. However, we are now moving into a technical age of standardised environments and reproducible environments supported by containerisation. The possibility of keeping stable functioning notebooks/software for longer periods of time and the ability to port across platforms is promising.

While Jupyter Notebooks can be a valuable resource, there are issues surrounding input data, processing, technical dependencies and quality. Poor quality notebooks with hidden dependencies may cause new users a lot of problems. The purpose of the D4.3 Jupyter Notebooks best practice document is to encourage the development of high quality Jupyter Notebooks, which are of genuine benefit to the broader community, in order to ensure their discoverability, accessibility and reusability. Critically it provides the standard and best practices to support the development of a repository that connects notebooks services and data. It also provides advice on the capture of metadata to delay technical obsolescence and improve portability. It employs an approach to graceful retirement to avoid the “library of broken things” effect.

We believe now is the time to pilot a repository for notebooks that can accommodate workflows, training materials and data set specific tools. We also need to factor some elements from the cross domain analysis such as factoring different service types and data formats. The ultimate goal would be to have a functioning repository and then assess its application to other software types. A software/tools repository is something that could evolve to be a core element of national infrastructure.

Training for undergraduates on the digital landscape

A key finding from the workshop was that awareness of data sources and analysis platforms was very low. This was in evidence from the PhD workshop and user surveys. Students have stated they would like more training on the digital landscape and thought this type of training should ideally begin at undergraduate level. We suspect the situation is also replicated in government and other types of research institutions. We make a recommendation that digital landscape training aimed at undergraduate students and governmental departments becomes a core part of the development of any National Data Library.

Future Studies

Due to the limited timescale of the project, there remain two key areas we would like to explore further:

LLM and Human in Loop AI for EDS data discovery

We are aware of the diversity and vocabularies currently in use with the EDS data centres and how this can become a barrier to data discovery. We are also aware of the disconnect between a dataset's potential application and how it has traditionally been described from a scientific perspective. We therefore recommend a study is required to evaluate merits of Human-in-the-loop (HITL) AI versus Large Language Models (LLMs) in supporting the discovery of EDS data by academic research communities and industry.

Single Sign on and security across Archives and Platforms

We have observed that the main users of UKRI data analysis platforms are UKRI funded projects; they are in particular attracted by the processing capabilities of these platforms. If we were to encourage a much broader user base conducting lighter weight analysis this would be beneficial. For example, CEDA training using the Jupyter Notebook service for students is restricted to training accounts for 100 students limited to a two week period. One of the reasons is that we wish to restrict full JASMIN access with its heavy processing capabilities. This is just one example of capacity/security/resource trade offs. We need to consider these aspects as we envisage broader use of our data in increased numbers. We recommend a study into single sign on/capacity/security and resource restriction to see if a common solution exists across archives and platforms.

Evolution DAPI WG to include University and Governmental Platforms

Through working group conversations we identified a number of other platforms we would like to engage with and have initiated conversations. The British Antarctic Survey & UK PDC¹³ are identifying future requirements for developing Digital Twins of the Polar Regions, research bases, the BAS research ship the RRS Sir David Attenborough and autonomous marine automated vehicles. We also initiated conversation with CReDo¹⁴ via the Energy Systems Catapult¹⁵. We anticipate that EDS data holdings could provide key data feeds to the digital twins and researchers using in outputs in areas such

We consider the inclusion of universities and key government departments as a vital part of the evolution of the working group. In anticipation of broader user groups, we need to ensure that our data holdings and tools can be effectively used in university or government departments. This will of course not be suitable in all scenarios and the capacity of centralized resources on UKRI platforms will also need to be considered. To support the strategic development of national infrastructure, the working group would need to evolve and have a rotating chair so that all groups are properly accommodated.

¹³ <https://www.bas.ac.uk/project/digital-twins-of-the-polar-regions/>

¹⁴ <https://digitaltwinhub.co.uk/climate-resilience-demonstrator-credo/>

¹⁵ <https://es.catapult.org.uk/>